

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: GOMEZ****FIRST NAME: ISMAEL****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 11)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. The process of academic essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-10)
2. Structure of academic essays (EUCLID 2021, 10-12)
3. Punctuations and language variants (EUCLID 2021, 15-22; 24-32)
4. Style guides (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)

WRITING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

I have reviewed the ACA-401D course and its contents. It provides a comprehensive preparatory course to communicate in the English language and prepares the student for the Ph.D. program in a conducive manner. The EUCLID approach enables students to be familiar with the fundamentals of language communications, style guides, and general academic writing. After reading the ACA-401 course pack for period one, I can submit that I have learned a lot from the course, especially key concepts as learning outcomes in response papers.

In this response paper, I will discuss the process and structure of academic writing and how the choice of English language variants and punctuation rules affect academic essay writing. Lastly, I will discuss the importance of style guides and avoiding plagiarism in academic essay writing.

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2) THE PROCESS OF WRITING ACADEMIC ESSAY

In academic essays, there are sequences/processes. The process of writing an academic or scholarly essay includes problem definition, resource gathering, critical thinking/reading, essay planning, and writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-14). I understand from the text that defining and analyzing the writing task at hand is advisable. This step may include a mental pre-assessment of what one already knows about the topic. Then, it may include analyzing initial thoughts about the topic at hand (EUCLID 2021, 7).

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After understanding and defining the writing task, the next step is to gather resources that expound the task. Resources for academic essays differ from other essays because of the scholarly context. Therefore, sources of facts for academic essays must be credible academic resources (EUCLID 2021, 8; The University of Sydney, n.d.). However, students must engage in critical reading and thinking to extract meaningful information from credible academic sources. In critical reading, the student identifies the writer's claim and how the claim is supported by empirical facts (University of York 2022). Critical thinking involves consciously applying established techniques to process gathered information (Foundation for Critical Thinking, n.d.). Hitchcock (2020) described critical thinking as "careful goal-directed thinking." In essence, critical thinking enables students to apply mental techniques in extracting goal-oriented information from academic resources.

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Identified information gathered needs to be organized in a writing plan or structure. Academic writers are advised to look at the question at hand while aligning with the information collected to find answers and evidence that support or disagree with the answer (EUCLID 2021, 9-10). The writing plan also involves ordering information in a logical scientific argumentative order (EUCLID 2021, 10). In short, EUCLID (2021, 10) argued that early writing, sentence planning, critical thinking on the question, and constant revision of drafts all contribute to the effective writing of essays.

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3) THE STRUCTURE OF ACADEMIC ESSAYS

Structures and frameworks guide academic essays to provide writers with effectiveness and consistency in presenting their ideas. EUCLID (2021, 10) suggests a format that includes an introduction, body, and conclusion. In the introduction section of academic essays, the writer is encouraged to include information like a short topic orientation. Other suggested information in the introduction includes positional statements about the topic and a general lead on how the other sections are organized (EUCLID 2021, 10).

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The body of the academic essay contains the details of the main ideas, including the pieces of evidence, analysis of the evidence, and leading statements to the next section of the body (EUCLID 2021, 10). The proper arrangement of these ideas into sections of main idea (M), pieces of evidence (E), analysis (A), and leading sentences (L) may help academic writers effectively communicate their ideas in paragraph structures (Duke

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University, n.d.). Writers should present their core arguments or positional statements in the main idea section of the paragraph (Duke University, n.d.). Moreover, writers should present academically established facts supporting or disagreeing with the evidence section's main idea. Further, the analysis section should synthesize the writer's understanding of the pieces of evidence. In contrast, the leading section enables the writer to put the paragraph in the context of the whole academic essay (Duke University, n.d.).

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In the conclusion section, the author restates their position about the question or writing task while summarizing the main points from the body section (EUCLID 2021, 10).

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4) LANGUAGE VARIANTS AND RULES OF ACADEMIC WRITING

Academic essay writing is guided by rules to ensure writers' right communication of ideas. Punctuations and language variants are two important rules that guide effective and consistent academic essay writing. Punctuations convey meanings to sentences (EUCLID 2021, 16). For example, the apostrophe conveys possession of singular nouns or indefinite pronouns. Apostrophes are also used to express contractions of two words in the English language. The bullet symbol is used in lists of words, phrases, or clauses that complete sentences. Depending on their position in a sentence, the colon and semi-colon determine the meanings of parts of the sentence. While the semi-colon links two related parts of a sentence, the colon connects unrelated parts. Commas have multiple usages, conveying sentence meanings (EUCLID 2021, 19-20). They are used to identify non-defining clauses, words, or phrases according to placement in sentences.

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EUCLID (2021, 25) suggests using a chosen language variant of the English language provides consistency and meaning in academic papers. The prominent variants are arguably the British and American variants (EUCLID 2021, 25). These two prominent variants may have different spellings of some words but the same pronunciation or vice-versa. Furthermore, some words may have the same spelling but may convey additional meanings when used in some contexts. Other differences include the usage of punctuation, collective nouns, and plural adjectives.

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5) STYLE GUIDES

Style guides adopt “rules and guidelines” to enforce consistency and expectation in academic essays (Purdue University, n.d.). The expected consistency may include sentence structure, font style, spelling standards, page layout and organization, heading formats, and many more (EUCLID 2021, 41; Purdue University, n.d.). Style guides come with templates that an organization recommends to stakeholders to achieve consistency in the documentation and expression of ideas and to aid portability among target audiences.

In the past, I have used the American Psychological Association (APA) style guide in writing academic essays. I find it rich in context and wide in usage, covering language elements and writing styles, especially in general management and psychology (Purdue University, n.d.) a). The APA style guide helps written communication in citing references, content organization, writing style, and discipline-dependent manuscripts (Purdue University, n.d. b). Further, Purdue University (n.d.) b) argued that though the APA manual is well adopted in the nursing, business, and social sciences disciplines, it offers a broad guideline that can be adopted in any discipline.

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6) PLAGIARISM

One of the core features of an academic paper is originality. Originality is the writer's ability to present and express their findings, deductions, and positions about a topic in their own words while crediting the information source. Plagiarism is when a writer fails to acknowledge the source of information in an academic paper (EUCLID 2021, 34). In other words, failure of an originality test can be regarded as plagiarism.

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In an academic paper, plagiarism can be expressed as direct quotes from a source, improper paraphrasing, or a direct copy of ideas without sufficiently referencing the source of information (EUCLID 2021, 34). Citations are established academic methods of avoiding plagiarism. Citations are implemented through in-text and a list of cited references. While the former references a block of ideas expressed through direct quotations or paraphrased contents, the latter compliments the former by providing a detailed list at the end of the academic paper.

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7) CONCLUSION

In developing an academic essay, there are sequences, processes, rules, and preferences one must follow as a student, especially the structure and process of developing/presenting an academic essay. The student must also be familiar with the rules and regulations of avoiding plagiarism and implementing and following a style guide when developing and writing academic essays. Also, how to consider punctuations and variants of the English language in presenting ideas. Academic essay writing is guided by rules that enable writers to communicate ideas because punctuations and language variants are important rules that guide effective and consistent academic essay writing.

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